

THE USE OF VISUAL AIDS IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH

Xoshimova Nargis Abdullayevna
Farg`ona davlat universiteti, dotsent
Toshmamatova Sitora
FarDu o‘qituvchisi

Annotation: The article is about authentic materials, aids, or tools should be used to motivate or increase learners’ interest. Audio-visual aids are sensitive tools and instructional devices. They are helpful in teaching and learning accents, pronunciation, articulation, grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure. Mobile apps are used for teaching or learning English language skills. Visual Aids types and their explanations. How we can use these types in learning and teaching English.

Keywords: Authentic Materials, Mobile Apps, Visual Aids. Flashcards, using pictures, realia, feely bags.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена аутентичным материалам, вспомогательным средствам или инструментам, которые следует использовать для мотивации или повышения интереса учащихся. Аудиовизуальные средства - это чувствительные инструменты и обучающие устройства. Они полезны при преподавании и изучении акцентов, произношения, артикуляции, грамматики, словарного запаса и структуры предложений. Мобильные приложения используются для преподавания или овладения навыками английского языка. Типы наглядных пособий и пояснения к ним. Как мы можем использовать эти типы в изучении и преподавании английского языка.

Ключевые слова: Аутентичные материалы, Мобильные приложения, Наглядные пособия. Карточки с использованием картинок, реалий, изящных сумочек.

In teaching and learning, it is difficult to define words without using visual representation that cause vagueness and perplexity in learner. Visual aids make smooth transition from one activity to another. Visual aids encourage the use of body language and eye movement. This added movement helps to give the speaker the control over the presentation. Using visual aids, then, is beneficial to both the learners and teacher. However visual aids using different kind of types and I will explain visual aids types one by one.

Flashcards. Flashcards are useful in the classroom in many subjects. Using visual aids in the classroom can be more beneficial than using the blackboards only in the lesson is more effective when using Flashcards with other graphic aids. Using the flashcards for class room teaching, the flash cards are to be properly used. The

following steps are used while displaying flash cards. First of all, give brief introduction about the lesson to students. Then, give instructions to students about their actions while flashing the cards. And other stage is, flash the card in front of the class by holding it high with both hands so that all the students can see it. Furthermore, let the student respond as per instructions already given. Lastly, review the lesson by selectively using flash cards.

Using pictures and Realia. Using pictures and realia in the classroom. pictures are the most commonly used and available graphical aids, pictures include photographs, painting, illustrations clipped from periodicals. They remind the learner of the meaning and help him/her communicate. They help the teacher as well save his/her voice. But too much detail confuses and distracts, while too little prevents recognition. Furthermore, realia it is real objects designed to be used in real life. Examples of realia which teachers can bring objects in classroom in order to support his/her words such as: clocks, food items, calendars, plastic fruits and vegetables, maps, household objects, real and play money, food containers and so on. In addition, it is used in teaching vocabulary and word meaning.

Feely bags. Using feely bags in the classroom. A multi-sensory feely bag activity is perfect for the development of oral language skills and vocabulary. In this Feely Bag can be any container that will hold an object unseen, to enable discussion to arise in order to solve the mystery, thus turning something simple into a deductive-reasoning activity. Nice examples are silk pillow cases, decorative cushion covers or any cloth bag or even a large shoe box which the pupils will enjoy decorating.

Tell a story. One of the most common ways to tell a story is to use illustrations so that the children can see them as they speak. New teachers regularly like this method since words can be written on the reverse side of the pictures to help the nervous teacher remember what to say. Unfortunately, usually too one of the most OVER-used methods and the temptation for the teacher is to under-prepare and after that be forced to read the words with little emotion or eye contact.

Using the board. Organizing and using the board. Even in classes where the teacher uses a PowerPoint presentation or any other type of technology, there could be a need for jotting down some words on the spot to show spelling or pronunciation, or simply for underlining some key concepts on the board. Moreover, using the board in our classes has many advantages: it encourages students to remember what they hear, allows teachers to illustrate and clarify information, and increases the students’ interest about the input they receive.

Using video. Using video in the classroom. Once the teacher has made the decision to use a video in class, they should think of the purpose of using it. There are some roles that the video can take in the classroom. Below are four possible roles for video in the classroom. Developing listening skills: Listening for global understanding

and listening for details. And, providing information: Providing content relevant to students’ needs and interests. Next one is, presenting or reinforcing language: Grammar, vocabulary, functions. However, using a video in the classroom may include more than one of these roles. students may watch a video to find out information about, for example, a famous person. The same lesson may also include work on developing listening skills to enable students to extract the relevant information. Students then can use it to develop vocabulary on the topic of ‘lives’.

All in all, we always need to be thoughtful and wise when picking anything for our student. Since one theory can be right with someone and not suitable for another. And don’t forget to add our personality in teaching, even with visual aids. Because proper visual aids can enhance visual communication and the effectiveness of your in-class teaching.

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